

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

TO DEVELOP AND VALIDATE UV-SPECTROSCOPIC METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF α -LIPOIC ACID AND L-GLUTATHIONE REDUCED USING METHYLENE BLUE AS A DERIVATIZING AGENT

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 04/04/2018

Available online
30/04/2018

Keywords

Chromophore,
Methylene Blue,
Leucomethylene Blue,
UV-Visible
Spectrophotometer,
Visible Region,
Non Chromophoric Drugs.

ABSTRACT

There are numerous drugs in the market that doesn't have chromophore due to which it is very difficult to estimate. And if possible, the method is either tedious or costly. Hence a new novel approach for the estimation of drugs can be developed for their estimation using methylene blue as a derivatizing agent. The reaction mechanism undergoes the formation of leucomethylene blue from methylene blue which is a colourless substance, which further reacts with the target drug and forms a coloured compound that can be estimated using UV-Visible Spectrophotometer in the visible region (400-800 nm). The resulting outcome is the estimation of non chromophoric drugs in the visible region which was not possible till date using methylene blue as a derivatizing agent. The conclusion of using this is method is - very cost effective and an easy method for estimation of drugs in the visible region which is not possible without it's derivatization. α -lipoic acid and L-Glutathione reduced were estimated at 663 nm with the linearity range of 20-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for α -lipoic acid and 200-600 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for L-Glutathione reduced.

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Please cite this article in press as **Pooja. D Dhruv** et al. To Develop and Validate Uv-Spectroscopic Method for the Estimation of α -Lipoic Acid and L-Glutathione Reduced Using Methylene Blue as A Derivatizing Agent. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(04).

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INTRODUCTION

The main aim of developing this method was the estimation of various drugs in the visible region (400-800 nm) that lack the chromophoric group. The two drugs, α -lipoic acid and L-Glutathione reduced lack the chromophore in their structure. Hence both of them were estimated using methylene blue as a derivatizing agent. They were estimated at 663 nm.

The main problem initially was the estimation of non-chromophoric drugs in the visible region. α -lipoic acid and L-Glutathione reduced does not have chromophoric group. So, method that is very cost effective and an easy method for estimation of drugs in the visible region for α -lipoic acid and L-Glutathione reduced has been developed. Hence the problem for the estimation of non-chromophoric drugs is been solved using this research.

Hence the main objective is to use methylene blue as a derivatizing agent for non-chromophoric drugs for its easy estimation. The research follows the following Reaction Mechanism:

For $-\text{COOH}$ group, bleaching of methylene blue occurs in dilute solution. In basic media, it is given by a pair of e^- belonging of N atom which receives H^+ results in resonance in which methylene blue molecule itself is reduced forming a Leucomethylene blue that leads to reduction in absorbance with increasing concentration. [1,2,3]

Fig 1 L-Glutathione reduced.

Fig 2 α -Lipoic acid.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials used:

Both the API were procured as: L-Glutathione reduced purchased from HI Media Gujarat, India and Alpha lipoic acid purchased from SRL Laboratories Gujarat, India.

Reagents used:

Solution of methylene blue (lab scale)
Solution of NH_4OH (finer grade)

Instrumentation:

Instruments used in the study were:

UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1800- Double beam spectrophotometer) with Quartz cuvette pair with 1 cm path length at 800 – 200 nm scanning range.

Experimental Methods:

Alpha lipoic acid

Preparation of methylene blue solution:

Accurately weighed quantity of 150 mg of methylene blue was transferred to a 250 ml volumetric flask then diluted upto mark with distilled water.

Selection of suitable wavelength for analysis:

Solution containing appropriate concentration of Alpha lipoic acid (10 μ g/ml) was prepared. With addition of 1ml NH₄OH and 1 ml solution of methylene blue, volume was made up with distilled water and was scanned using UV spectrophotometer in "Spectrum mode" in the range of 800 – 200 nm. Detection Wavelength: 663 nm

Preparation of working standard stock solution of Alpha lipoic acid

Accurately weighed quantity of 100 mg of Alpha lipoic acid was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask then diluted upto mark with distilled water. 10 ml of the above solution was further diluted to 50 ml with distilled water having final concentration of 200 μ g/ml.

Preparation of calibration curve

From the above stock solution 1,2,3,4 and 5 ml drug solution were transferred in different 10 ml volumetric flasks. To all these solutions, 1ml NH₄OH and 1 ml solution of methylene blue was added and volume was made up with distilled water having final concentration of 20,40,60,80 and 100 μ g/ml.

Spectra of increasing concentration were taken. Absorbance of prepared standard solutions were measured at 663 nm.

Fig 3: Zero order overlaid spectra of Alpha lipoic acid (20-100 μ g/ml) at λ_{max} 663 nm.

Table 1: Linearity Data of Alpha lipoic acid at 663 nm.

Sr. no.	Concentration (gm/100ml)	Absorbance* \pm SD	%RSD
1	0.002	0.8228 \pm 0.0007	0.0909
2	0.004	0.7372 \pm 0.0007	0.1015
3	0.006	0.6382 \pm 0.0007	0.1172
4	0.008	0.5210 \pm 0.0010	0.2102
5	0.01	0.4338 \pm 0.0007	0.1725

Fig 4: Calibration curve of Alpha lipoic acid at 663 nm.

Table 2: Result of Calibration curve of Alpha lipoic acid by methylene blue method.

Parameter	Alpha lipoic acid
Regression	$y = -52.09x + 0.9384$
Equation at λ_{max} 663 nm	
Correlation coefficient at λ_{max} 663 nm	0.9964

Table 3: Result of Range, Linearity, LOD and LOQ study for Methylene blue method.

Parameter	Alpha lipoic acid
Range	20– 100 µg/ml
Linearity equation	$y = -52.09x + 0.9384$
Regression coefficient	0.9964
LOD (µg/ml)	4.4792
LOQ (µg/ml)	13.5735

Table 4: Repeatability study for Methylene blue method.

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (n=6)
60	0.6382
60	0.639
60	0.637
60	0.638
60	0.639
60	0.638
Mean absorbance	0.6382
SD	0.0007
%RSD	0.1172

Table 5: Result of intraday precision for Methylene blue method:

Conc. (µg/ml)	Mean Absorbance* ± SD	%RSD
48	0.540±0.0007	0.1068
60	0.639±0.0007	0.1172
72	0.732±0.0007	0.1260
Average % RSD		0.1166

Table 6: Result of Interday precision for Methylene blue method:

Conc. (µg/ml)	Mean Absorbance* ± SD	%RSD
48	0.540±0.0007	0.1078
60	0.699±0.0007	0.1182
72	0.757±0.0007	0.1360
Average % RSD		0.1206

Table 7 Result of accuracy of Alpha lipoic acid for Methylene blue method:

Level of Recovery (n=3)	Amount of sample taken (µg/ml)	Amount of std added (µg/ml)	Total amount (µg/ml)	Recovery of Alpha lipoic acid	%Recovery	SD	%RSD
0%	36	0	36	-	-	-	-
	Mean% recovery						
80%	36	12	48	47.98	99.93	0.2940	0.2947
				47.79	99.35		
				48.02	100.01		
	Mean% recovery						
100%	36	24	60	59.98	99.94	0.1902	0.1908
				59.67	99.49		
				59.23	99.61		
	Mean% recovery						
120%	36	36	72	71.94	99.97	0.0205	0.0205
				72.05	100.02		
				72.01	100.00		
	Mean% recovery						
					99.99		

Analysis of pharmaceutical formulation

Average weight of 20 tablets were taken. Powder was triturated. Weight equivalent to 100 mg Alpha lipoic acid was transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up with distilled water. 10 ml of the above solution was further diluted to 50 ml with water having the final concentration of 200 µg/ml. 3 ml of above solution was taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask to obtain final concentration of 60 µg/ml. To this 1ml NH₄OH and 1 ml solution of methylene blue was added and volume was made up with distilled water. Solution was sonicated for 15 minutes and was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 41. The absorbance of prepared sample solution at 663nm was taken. The analysis procedure was repeated six times with formulation. Relative concentration in the sample was calculated using equation of Beer-Lambert Law,

$A = A_{1\%} / 1 \text{ cm} * bc$ eq (1) Where,

A=absorbance of Alpha lipoic acid at 663 nm

A_{1%/1 cm}=Molar absorptivity

b=path length of radiation through sample (cm)

c=concentration of Alpha lipoic acid in sample (gm/100 ml)

From the calibration curve the absorptivity was calculated from the slope. By putting values in equation 1, concentration in gm/100 ml was obtained.

Fig 5: Spectrum of sample by Methylene blue method.

Table 8 Analysis of Pharmaceutical formulation: (n=6).

Labelled claim(mg)	Amount obtained (mg)	% label claim
Alpha lipoic acid	Alpha lipoic acid	Alpha lipoic acid
100	99.99	99.99
100	99.96	99.96
100	98.79	98.79
100	99.99	99.99
100	100.01	100.01
100	99.98	99.98

Drug	Mean % Labelled claim (n=6)± SD	%RSD
Alpha lipoic acid	99.7866±0.4459	0.4469

L-Glutathione reduced

Preparation of methylene blue solution

Accurately weighed quantity of 150 mg of methylene blue was transferred to a 250 ml volumetric flask then diluted upto mark with distilled water.

Selection of suitable wavelength for analysis

Solution containing appropriate concentration of L-Glutathione reduced (50µg/ml) were prepared. To this, 1ml NH₄OH and 1 ml solution of methylene blue was added and volume was made up with distilled water and were scanned using UV spectrophotometer in "Spectrum mode" in the range of 800 – 200 nm.

Preparation of working standard solution of L-Glutathione reduced

Accurately weighed quantity of 1000 mg of L-Glutathione reduced was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask then diluted upto mark with distilled water. 5 ml of above solution was further diluted to 50 ml volumetric flask with distilled water having final concentration of 2000µg/ml.

Preparation of calibration curve

From the above stock solution 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5 and 3 ml drug solution were transferred in different 10 ml volumetric flasks. To all these solutions, 1ml NH₄OH and 1 ml solution of methylene blue was added and volume was made up with distilled water having final concentration of 200,300,400,500 and 600 µg/ml. Spectra of increasing concentration were taken. Absorbance of prepared standard solutions were measured at 663 nm.

Fig 6: Zero order overlaid spectra of L-Glutathione reduced (200-600 µg/ml) at λmax.663 nm

Table 9: Linearity Data of L-Glutathione reduced at 663 nm.

Sr. no.	Concentration (gm/100ml)	Absorbance*± SD	%RSD
1	0.020	0.9140±0.0007	0.07990
2	0.030	0.8470±0.0008	0.10559
3	0.040	0.7648±0.0006	0.08932
4	0.050	0.6942±0.0006	0.09840
5	0.060	0.6120±0.0004	0.07307

Fig 7: Calibration curve of L-Glutathione reduced at 663 nm.

Table 10: Result of Calibration curve of L-Glutathione reduced by methylene blue method.

Parameter	L-Glutathione reduced
Regression	$y = -7.568x + 1.0691$
Equation at λ_{max} 663 nm	
Correlation coefficient at λ_{max} 663 nm	0.9989

Table 11: Result of Range, Linearity, LOD and LOQ study for Methylene blue method.

Parameter	L-Glutathione reduced
Range	200– 600 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
Linearity equation	$y = -7.568x + 1.0691$
Regression coefficient	0.9989
LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	51.1810
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	155.094

Table 12: Repeatability study for Methylene blue method.

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (n=6)
400	0.764
400	0.764
400	0.765
400	0.765
400	0.766
400	0.766
Mean absorbance	0.7648
SD	0.0006
%RSD	0.0893

Table 13: Result of intraday precision for Methylene blue method:

Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean Absorbance* \pm SD	%RSD
320	0.6556 \pm 0.0004	0.0718
400	0.7645 \pm 0.0001	0.2222
480	0.8310 \pm 0.0008	0.0982
Average % RSD		0.0641

Table 14: Result of Interday precision for Methylene blue method:

Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean Absorbance* \pm SD	%RSD
320	0.6863 \pm 0.0004	0.0686
400	0.7788 \pm 0.0004	0.0605
480	0.8446 \pm 0.0004	0.0558
Average % RSD		0.0616

Table 15: Result of accuracy of L-Glutathione reduced for Methylene blue method:

Level of Recovery (n=3)	Amount of sample taken (µg/ml)	Amount of std added (µg/ml)	Total amount (µg/ml)	Recovery of L-Glutathione reduced	%Recovery	SD	%RSD
0%	240	0	240	-	-	-	-
	Mean% recovery						
80%	240	80	320	319.99	99.99	0.0169	0.017
				319.88	99.96		
				320.01	100.00		
	Mean% recovery						
100%	240	160	400	399.99	99.99	1.1953	1.2160
				389.98	97.49		
				389.69	97.42		
	Mean% recovery						
120%	240	240	480	479.99	99.99	0.9947	0.9881
				479.78	99.95		
				490.01	101.08		
	Mean% recovery						
					99.67		

Analysis of pharmaceutical formulation

Average weight of 20 tablets were taken. Tablet was crushed and triturated. Weight equivalent to 1000 mg L-Glutathione reduced was transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up with distilled water. 5 ml of the above solution was further diluted to 50 ml with distilled water. 2 ml of the above solution was taken. To this 1ml NH₄OH and 1 ml solution of methylene blue was added and volume was made up with distilled water to obtain final concentration of 400 µg/ml. Solution was sonicated for 15 minutes and was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 41. The absorbance of prepared sample solution at 663nm was taken. The analysis procedure was repeated six times with formulation. Relative concentration in the sample was calculated using equation of Beer-Lambert Law,

$$A=A1\%/1cm*bc \dots\dots eq(1)$$

Where,

A=absorbance of L-Glutathione reduced at 663 nm

A1%/1cm=Molar absorptivity

b=path length of radiation through sample (cm)

c=concentration of L-Glutathione reduced in sample (gm/100 ml)

From the calibration curve the absorptivity was calculated from the slope. By putting values in equation 1, concentration in gm/100 ml was obtained.

Fig 8: Spectrum of sample by Methylene blue method.

Table 16: Analysis of Pharmaceutical formulation: (n=6).

Labelled claim(mg)	Amount obtained (mg)	% label claim
L-Glutathione reduced	L-Glutathione reduced	L-Glutathione reduced
500	499.99	99.99
500	498.62	99.72
500	499.00	99.80
500	497.31	99.46
500	499.57	99.91
500	499.98	99.99

Drug	Mean % Labelled claim (n=6)± SD	%RSD
L-Glutathione reduced	99.8110±0.1850	0.1854

Method validation:

Validation of developed method was carried out according to ICH guideline for validation of Analytical Procedures Q2 (R1):

Linearity

Solutions having concentration 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 µg/ml for Alpha lipoic acid and 200,300,400,500 and 600 µg/ml L-Glutathione reduced were prepared from working standard solution. Prepared solutions were analyzed as per the proposed method. Five replicate analyses were carried out. The mean absorbance with its standard deviation and % relative standard deviation were calculated. Mean absorbance against concentration were plotted to obtain the calibration curves. Regression equations, co- relation coefficients were computed from calibration curves.

Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ):

LOD and LOQ were calculated from the data obtained from the linearity studies. For each of the five replicate determinations, slope and y-intercept of the linearity plot was determined. Average of slope (S) and standard deviation of the y intercept (σ) was computed. From these values, the parameters LOD and LOQ were determined using following equations (On the basis of response and slope of the regression equation):

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \sigma \backslash S$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma \backslash S$$

Where; σ = Standard deviation of Response,
S = Slope of calibration curve

Precision:**Repeatability:**

Six replicate solutions containing 60 µg/ ml Alpha lipoic acid and 400 µg/ ml L-Glutathione reduced were prepared. Prepared solutions were analysed as per the proposed method. The mean % labelled claim with its standard deviation and % relative standard deviation were computed.

Intermediate precision:

Intra-day precision and Inter-day precision were determined in terms of % RSD. Intraday precision was determined by analysing Alpha lipoic acid and L-Glutathione reduced for three times in the same day. Interday precision was hence determined by analysing Alpha lipoic acid and L-Glutathione reduced at three independent concentration level of their respective calibration range for three days.

Intraday Precision:

Replication within same day at different time: Sample solution containing Alpha lipoic acid as 48 µg/ml, 60 µg/ml and 72 µg/ml and L-Glutathione reduced as 320 µg/ml, 400 µg/ml and 480 µg/ml in sample were analyzed for 3 times on the same days and %RSD were calculated.

Accuracy:

Accuracy was calculated by addition of standard drug to pre-analyzed sample at 3 different concentration level and computing percentage recoveries. Accuracy was assessed using 9 determinations over 3 concentration levels covering the specified range (e.g., 3 concentrations and 3 replicates each of the total analytical procedure). Prepared solutions were analyzed as per the proposed method to have final level of 80%, 100% and 120% and % recoveries were calculated by proposed method. The mean percentage recovery with its standard deviation and % relative standard deviation were computed at each level.

CONCLUSION

“The above research suggests that new and novel method for estimation of various non-chromophoric drugs has been developed using a single derivatizing agent, methylene blue. The method can be used in routine Quality Assurance and estimation of Alpha lipoic acid and L-Glutathione reduced.”

List of abbreviations

USP	-United States Pharmacopoeia
%RSD	-Percentage relative standard deviation
LOD	-Limit of Detection
LOQ	-Limit of Quantitation

Conflict of interests

None conflict the given data

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my esteemed Guide Dr. Parula B. Patel (Principal of S. J. Thakkar Pharmacy College, Rajkot), for providing me with unfailing support, excellence guidance and continuous encouragement throughout my years of study and through the process of researching and writing this thesis.

REFERENCES

1. Nguyen KC. Quantitative analysis of COOH-terminated alkanethiol SAMs on gold nanoparticle surfaces. *Adv. Nat. Sci.: Nanosci. Nanotechnol.* 2012; 3:1-5.
2. Kelner MJ and Alexander NM. Methylene Blue Directly Oxidizes Glutathione without the Intermediate Formation of Hydrogen Peroxide. *J. Biol. Chem.* 1985; 260(28):15168-15171.
3. Elkheir AA, Saleh HM, El-henawee MM and Ghareeb BS. Spectrophotometric determination of Terbinafine HCl, Telmisartan and ramipril through redox reactions using bromate-bromide mixture. *IJPCBS.* 2015; 5(1):328-346.

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